

EFFECT OF INTERFACIAL DAMAGE ON RESIDUAL TENSILE STRENGTH FOR SCS-6/TI-15-3 METAL MATRIX COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY: Effect of thermal cycling is discussed on the performance of a metal matrix composite with special emphasis on the interfacial degradation between fiber and matrix. Material used in this study was Ti-15V-3Cr-3Al-3Sn alloy matrix reinforced by SiC fiber (SCS-6/Ti-15-3 MMC) fabricated by HIP method at 880°C. The thermal cycling test was performed at the temperature range from 380°C to 880°C under 2 holding times. After thermal cycling the residual tensile strength was determined and the fracture surface was examined by a SEM.

The interfacial reaction layer thickness increased with increasing the total holding time for both aging at 880°C and thermal cycling test. The residual tensile strength for thermal cycling test drastically decreased with increasing the cycling number up to about 100 cycles and the strength tended to be saturate over 100 cycles. The shear strength estimated by multiple fracture theory on the basis of the interval of fractured fiber also decreased with increasing cycling number. The residual tensile strength estimated by the modified rule of mixture on the basis of the average fiber strength was equal to the experimental data for as received material and thermal cycling of 24 cycles under the holding time of 60 minutes, while for 240 cycles the estimated value from the minimum strength of the fiber was the same as the experimental one. It is suggested that for the shorter cycling range the multiple fracture would occur during the tensile test, while for the longer cycling range the weakest fiber breakage would lead to catastrophic failure of composite.

KEYWORDS: Metal matrix composites (MMC), Titanium alloy based MMC, Interfacial reaction layer, Interfacial shear stress, Thermal cycling, Residual tensile strength

INTRODUCTION

Titanium matrix alloy composites are one of the most promising materials for high temperature structural applications such as gas turbine components. However, the use of these materials for turbine engine applications often depends on their ability to withstand both cyclic loading and thermal cycling, especially the thermal cycling damages induced from the mismatch of the thermal expansion coefficients between fiber and matrix. On the other hand, the load cycling damages are induced by the starting or stopping of turbine engine. Actually the machines are affected with both thermal cycling and load cycling. There are a few reports concerning the fatigue strength, the fatigue crack propagation properties tested at room temperature and thermo-mechanical properties, while there are very few reports about the degradation of the SCS-6/Ti metal matrix composite (MMC) under thermo-mechanical conditions. According to Johnson et al., the thermo-mechanical damage was not so predominant up to 2000 cycles tested from 93°C to 650°C under in-phase and out-of-phase for SCS-6/Ti-15-3 MMC[1]. As far as we know, there has been no report to discuss the effect of thermal cycling damage on the mechanical properties for SCS-6/Ti-15-3 MMC.

Therefore we referred to another MMC system as follows. The post tensile strength decreased with increasing thermal cycling after 153°C to 815°C thermal cycling test for SCS-6/Ti-24-11 MMC[2]. The effects of the thermal cycling or load cycling at high temperature on the degradation of those composites were not yet clearly shown.

To discuss the effect of the thermal cycling on the interfacial degradation, the SCS-6/Ti-15-3 MMC was tested under the temperature range from 380°C to 880°C in vacuum in this paper. After the thermal cycling test the residual tensile strength was determined and the interfacial reaction thickness, the interval of fractured fiber in composite were also examined. The interfacial shear stress, the residual tensile strength of composite were estimated.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The material studied here was Ti-15V-3Cr-3Al-3Sn alloy matrix with the continuous SiC fiber reinforcement at an average volume fraction of 0.3 (SCS-6/Ti-15-3 MMC). The composite was processed using the foil/fiber/foil consolidation process and the materials was supplied from Mitsubishi Heavy Industries, Japan. The SiC fiber was composed of b-SiC deposited on a 40 mm carbon monofilament substrate with a double pass carbon-rich coating applied to the fiber surface for chemical compatibility consolidations. The Ti-15V-3Cr-3Al-3Sn alloy, as processed in foil form, consists of the b-phase. The composite was fabricated by HIP method at 880°C under 100 MPa for 1.5 hour. The solution treatment and aging treatment were performed at 780°C for 30 min and 482°C for 1000 min, respectively, to stabilize microstructures of the Matrix. Photograph 1 shows the optical micrographs of the polished section of the composite perpendicular to fiber axis. The micrograph indicates that the SiC fiber is hexagonal aligned in the matrix without touching other fibers.

As received composites were in a form of plates, with a thickness of 2.5mm. From those plates (130 mm x 200 mm) specimens were machined to a width of 9 mm and a length of 55

Photo. 1 Cross sectional micrograph of SCS-6/Ti-15-3 MMC.

mm. The fiber axis was located in the longitudinal direction of the specimen. The central part of the specimen was machined to reduce the thickness to 1.2 mm and 10mm length. Shape and dimension of the specimen are shown in Fig. 1. Thermal cycling test was

performed using the image heating furnace at the temperature range from 380°C and 880°C in vacuum under 2 holding times of 6 min and 60 min. The heating and cooling rates were 500°C/min. Fig. 2 shows a schematic drawing of heat cycles used in this experiment. After thermal cycling test, the tensile strength was evaluated at room temperature. The tensile test was performed using an Instron type testing machine with a crosshead speed of 0.5mm/min. After the test, The fracture surface and side surface near fracture plane were observed using a scanning electron microscope (SEM). The thickness of interfacial reaction layer was measured on the transverse cross sectional surfaces before and after thermal cycling tests. Moreover the push-out test was performed on the cross sectional thin plate cut from the thermal cycling specimen after test and the strength of the dissolved fiber from the composite was also examined after thermal cycling test.

Fig. 1 Specimen figure

Fig. 2 Thermal cycling conditions

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Reaction layer thickness

Photograph 2 shows the typical example of the cross sectional optical micrographs of

the composite for as received and thermal cycled. The gray part shows the SiC mantle and its outer circumferential black ring shows the carbon coating layer. The white area shows the matrix. On the Photo. 2(a) the black circular area shows the carbon core filament. The SiC fiber, outer carbon coating layer were clearly found on the photographs. A dark weak line was seen outside of the carbon coating layer. A zone between carbon coating layer and the dark line is reaction layer. The thickness of reaction layer increased with increasing total holding time at 880°C.

Figure 3 shows the variation of reaction layer thickness to the total holding time at 880°C. In the figure the data after aging at 880°C were also included. The composite material was HIPed at 880°C for 1.5 hour. In this condition the reaction layer thickness was 0.8 mm. The reaction layer thickness linearly increased with increasing holding time as shown in Fig. 3. Moreover, the reaction layer thickness after thermal cycling test was nearly the same as that after aging. It is suggested that the reaction between fiber and matrix would be controlled by diffusion of element included in both materials.

The reaction layer thickness was examined at 930°C and 980°C and the activation energy was estimated to about 243kJ/mol. This value was very high in comparison to the previous data[3]

Photo. 2 Micrographs of reaction layer for SCS-6/Ti-15-3 MMC.

Fig. 3 Variation of reaction layer thickness to total holding time for SCS-6/Ti-15-3 MMC

Residual tensile strength

After thermal cycling the residual tensile strength was examined and the results are shown in Fig. 4. In Fig. 4 (b) for total holding time of 100 hours the strength of virgin material was about 1.8 GPa and the elongation was about 1.1%. After thermal cycling of 1000 cycles the strength decreased to about 1.2 GPa in comparison for virgin material. But the results after 100 and 1000 cycles were not so different. In Fig. 4(a) shown the results for total holding time of 24 hours the strengths for after 24 and 240 cycles were about 1.6 and 1.2 GPa, respectively, while the elongation of 240 cycles was much shorter than that of 24 cycles. It is suggested that the tensile strength and elongation would be influenced by the thermal cycling number.

Fig. 4 Residual tensile stress to strain of SCS-6/Ti-15-3 MMC for (a) 100 hrs and (b) 24 hrs.

Figure 5 shows the relationship between the residual tensile strength and thermal cycling. In this figure, the data for holding time of 6 and 60 minutes are plotted with different symbols and datum for as received materials is also plotted. The residual tensile strength

was drastically decreased with increasing thermal cycling number and the strength saturated to be about 1.2 GPa over 100 cycles. For SCS-6/Ti-24Al-11Nb composite[2] the residual tensile strength after thermal cycling also drastically decreased with increasing cycle up to about 500 cycles and saturated to nearly zero over 500 cycles. In this case the alternate temperature range was 665°C from 150°C to 815°C and tested in air which are different with this study. Many transverse cracks were observed on the specimen surface after 500 thermal cycles, while in our study none were observed.

Fig.5 Relationship between residual tensile strength and thermal cycling number for SCS-6/Ti-15-3 MMC

Figure 6 shows the residual tensile strength after aging and thermal cycling for SCS-6/Ti-15-

Fig. 6 Variation of residual tensile strength to thermal cycling for SCS-6/Ti and Ti alloy MMC

3MMC are compared with reported data for SCS-6/Ti-6-4 MMC, SCS-6/Ti MMC[4]. SCS-6/Ti-6-4 MMC and SCS-6/Ti MMC were tested in the temperature range from 350°C to 850°C for thermal cycling and aging test was performed at 850°C. These testing conditions were different from our study, but the alternated temperature range for thermal cycling was the same for both. Therefore those data were plotted on the same figure to be compared with our data. For aging condition the strengths of SCS-6/Ti-6-4 and SCS-6/Ti MMC's linearly decrease with increasing time. But after thermal cycling the strength for SCS-6/Ti-6-4 MMC drastically decreases over 6 hours and saturates after it. For SCS-6/Ti MMC the strength linearly decreased with increasing time up to about zero MPa. For our results the strength for the holding time of 60 min was higher than that for 6 min, but for the holding time of 100 hours the strength was nearly the same for both holding times. It is suggested that the resistance of thermal cycling is higher for SCS-6/Ti-15-3 MMC than those for SCS-6/Ti-6-4 MMC and SCS-6/Ti MMC in spite of lower maximum holding temperature.

Intervals of fractured fibers

Photograph 3 shows the micrographs of the side surface of the specimen. The white areas were the matrix and gray bar or acicular was silicon carbide fiber. In the upper side of the micrographs is fracture surface where some pull out fibers were found. The transverse cracks on the fiber were also seen. The interval of the fractured fiber was examined on the micrographs except for near final fracture surface.

Photo. 3 Micrographs of fractured fiber after thermal cycling observed on the side surface of the specimen for SCS-6/Ti-15-3 MMC.

Figure 7 shows the relationship between the probability and interval of the fractured fiber. The data was plotted on the log-normal probability paper. The dispersion of data for virgin materials was less than those for 240 and 1000 cycles. The average intervals increased with increasing cycles.

Fig. 7 Probability of interval of the fractured fiber in SCS-6/Ti-15-3 MMC.

Interfacial shear stress

The interfacial shear stress was estimated by the multiple fracture theory based on the following equation[5].

$$x = (V_m/V_f)(\sigma_{m,u}R_f/2\tau) \tag{1}$$

where V_m and V_f are the volume fractions of matrix and fiber, respectively and $\sigma_{m,u}$ and τ are ultimate strength of matrix and shear stress, respectively. R_f is the radius of the fiber.

Figure 8 shows the variation of shear stress to thermal cycles for SCS-6/Ti-15-3 MMC. The

Fig. 8 Estimated shear stress after thermal cycling for SCS-6/Ti-15-3 MMC.

shear stress also drastically decreased with increasing cycles. The trend of the shear stress is nearly same as the residual tensile strength shown in Fig. 5.

Estimation of residual tensile strength of SCS-6/Ti-15-3 MMC

The modified mixed rule of composites was proposed by Kagawa et al.[6] and could be written.

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_f [1 - (R_f \sigma_f / (2 \tau L_g))] V_f + \sigma_m (1 - V_f) \quad (2)$$

where σ_c , σ_f , and σ_m are the strength of composite, fiber and the strength of matrix at fracture of composite, respectively. σ_f is the average strength of fiber. L_g is the gauge length.

In this case the fiber strength was not obtained. In order to estimate the strength of composite after thermal cycling test the fiber strength after aging was used. The average fiber strengths for virgin material and after 24 hours aging were about 4.76 GPa and 3.68 GPa. Moreover the maximum and minimum fiber strengths were also used.

The estimated values and bands of strength were also designated in Fig.9. For as received materials and 24 cycles tested at the holding time of 60 min the estimated values from average fiber strength are nearly equal to the experimental ones. On the other hand, for 240 cycles tested at the holding time of 6 min the estimated value from the minimum fiber strength was nearly the same as the experimental one. It is suggested that the residual strength of composite for short cycling number could be estimated by the average fiber strength, but for longer cycling number the residual strength of composite would be controlled by the weakest fiber, when the weakest fiber included in composite would be broken at first, suddenly the whole fracture of composite would be induced.

Fig. 9 Estimated residual tensile strength after thermal cycling for SCS-6/Ti-15-3 MMC.

CONCLUSIONS

- 1) The reaction layer thickness of the composite linearly increases with increasing the time for both of aging or thermal cycling conditions. It is suggested that the interfacial reaction would be controlled by diffusion of elements included in composite. The activation energy was also estimated to 240 kJ/mol.
- 2) The residual tensile strength after thermal cycling test drastically decreased with increasing

cycle number up to about 100 cycles. After that the strength tended to be saturated up to about 1,000 cycles. The effect of holding time on the residual strength was not so significant. It is suggested that the thermal cycling effect is very significant to residual strength of composite.

3) The interval of fractured fiber was examined on the side surface near tensile fracture surfaces. The intervals increased with increasing thermal cycling number.

The shear stress after thermal cycling was estimated by the multiple fracture theory on the basis of the interval of the fractured fiber. The shear stress also drastically decreased with increasing the thermal cycling number.

4) The residual tensile strength of composite was estimated by the modified rule of mixture on the basis of the average, maximum and minimum fiber strength extracted from the composite after aging test. For shorter cycle range the best estimation of composite strength was obtained using the average fiber strengths, while for the longer cycling range the minimum fiber strength leads to a better agreement with experimental data. It is suggested that for the shorter cycling range the multiple fracture process would occur, while for longer cycling range the weakest fiber would be broken at first, the catastrophic fracture of composite would be induced.

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